

IOT BASED SMART TABLET SORTER

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Abstract—An IoT-based innovative medicine dispenser prototype model designed to assist patients and dependent senior citizens in taking their medications on time, without fail, and eliminating the chance of over or under dosing. The device alarms patients to correctly and accurately take suitable medication, reducing the risk of late recovery, severe disease, and even death. It also provides instant communication between caretakers and patients, ringing the alarm signal when the patient's medication is due.

Keywords—Automated medication sorting , Real Time clock , Drug dispensing system , Low risk, Alarm signal

I. INTRODUCTION

The global population of people aged 60 years and older is expected to grow by 250% in 2050, leading to an increase in long-term healthcare expenditures. To maintain a healthy aging population, assistive health technology (AHT) is being employed to improve healthcare systems. Rapid technological advances will revolutionize research in human health, enabling new approaches to monitor human health, behavior, and activity. Medication adherence is an important component of health and well-being, with numerous studies showing the importance of adequate medication adherence. Achieving healthy aging requires several important strategies, including correct medication adherence, which is mainly related to individual behavior. However, medication adherence remains a common issue within the healthcare sector, especially among older adults who are living with multiple chronic illnesses. Routine monitoring and assessment of the individual's adherence is crucial to improving their health outcomes. Current assessment methods for medication adherence have advantages and limitations. Advancements in public health and medicine are leading to a significant increase in the life span and population

division of older adults, creating challenges in managing care. A recent study estimated that the annual gain of adults aged 65 and above will exceed 10 million globally, with over 60 countries having around 2 million people in this group by 2030. Pill-dispensing machines, designed to be reliable, easy to use, and useful in personal medication management, are being used to address this issue. The Intelligent Medicine Box is a healthcare product that uses an affordable IoT-powered medicine box and an Android application. The app allows users to start new medications, store treatment details, and schedule appointments with doctors. It also features an inbuilt prescription feature, making it beneficial during pandemic times. Users can also add custom treatment plans. The box alerts users at the right time to take the medicine, produces audio, and illuminates the correct container number, making it fool proof. This innovative solution reduces the care giver's burden in the healthcare sector.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Advancements in public health and medicine have led to a significant increase in the life span and population division of older adults, creating challenges in managing efficient care for them. A recent study estimated that the annual gain of adults aged 65 and above will exceed 10 million globally, with over 60 countries having around 2 million people in this group by 2030. Pill-dispensing machines, which are reliable, easy to use, and useful in personal medication management, are used to give patients medicine according to a predetermined schedule. Previous work has used Arduino (AT Mega328P) for a simple electronic reminder system with a rectangle box divided into three equal sub-boxes with LEDs and buzzers. The system uses LCD, GSM, and RTC modules for display, communication, and time tracking.

Othman, Nurmiza Binti, proposed a pill dispenser with an alarm via smartphone notification, which consists of a 5 V power supply, a button, an RTC module, and an IR sensor to count the medicine. Arduino's novelty is that it can perform a basic health check on the patient, unlike previous designs that could only be used by one person. This biometric verification allows multiple users to use the device, giving it an advantage over existing designs. [1]

The global population of people aged 60 years and older is expected to grow by 250% in 2050, leading to an increase in long-term healthcare expenditures. As a result, the employment of assistive health technology (AHT) is increasing to maintain a healthy aging population. Rapid technological advances will revolutionize research in human health, enabling new approaches to monitor human health, behaviour, and activity. Medication adherence is an important component of health and well-being, with numerous studies showing the importance of adequate medication adherence. Achieving healthy aging requires several important strategies, including correct medication adherence, which is mainly related to individual behaviour. However, medication adherence remains a common issue within the healthcare sector, especially among older adults, who are living with multiple chronic illnesses. Routine monitoring and assessment of an individual's adherence is crucial to improving their health outcomes. Current assessment methods for medication adherence have advantages and limitations. This review paper provides insights into medication adherence monitoring technologies and addresses open research challenges for further improvement. The literature review approach used in this paper follows an iterative and incremental procedure, finding and including new studies about medication adherence monitoring technologies and approaches to the surveyed studies. The paper divides the present paper into several sections based on the main monitoring or sensing technology used and compares different medication adherence monitoring techniques and approaches related to accuracy, energy efficiency, and user comfort. Given the importance of technology embodiment in medication adherence systems, this paper addresses the need for researchers and investigators in healthcare monitoring in both engineering and medical societies. The paper is organized as follows: the following 8 Section introduces some background about the concept of medication adherence; existing reviews on medication adherence are discussed; technology-based systems for medication adherence monitoring are described; challenges and future trends associated with these approaches are discussed; and the last section concludes the paper. [2]

T. Arun Prasad et al. proposed a smart medicine box that monitors patient heart rate and temperature, sends emergency alerts and SMS alerts to caregivers and doctors, and stores patient information. Danyllo V. da Silva et al. used LEDs to indicate the box's opening and a buzzer for audible reminders. C. Ram Kumar et al. had a vitals calculation box with minimal software and hardware requirements. Shinde S. et al. proposed a smart pill box with a reminder and

consumption function, allowing users to take pills at specific times. Mohammed Abdul Kader et al. deployed a weekly medicine box for three people with 21 airtight containers. Doshi et al. proposed a pill reminder box, helping patients take their medicines correctly. KS Angel et al. focused on the computerization of the medicine box using a PIC16F877A controller and Bluetooth for Android connectivity. Yash Sharma et al. suggested a simple medicine box with an audible reminder when it's time to take medicine. Sriivas et al. proposed an IoT healthcare platform with smart medicine boxes for monitoring patients' health. S. Jaipriya et al. suggested an intelligent medicine box with vital calculations and dose remainders at appropriate times. Ben-bin Chen et al. proposed a circular medicine box with an Android app and touch screen for use without a phone. The TriCELLA pillbox contains a box that sends notifications through a mobile application. WISEPILL is widely used for diseases like HIV and tuberculosis, storing patient data, providing notifications about medication timing, and allowing doctors to check patient status. [3]

An automatic pill dispenser is a device that dispenses medical pills with different administration schedules. It includes multiple pill storage compartments, an automatic release mechanism, and a pill receptacle. The dispenser generates a signal to alert the patient to take the dispensed medicine. Twelve storage compartments are preloaded with all prescribed pills for a 24-hour period. The patient loads pills into each compartment according to the administration schedule. The dispenser then rotates the compartments over a trapdoor, emptying each one. A photoelectric detector detects pills and alerts the patient with an audible or visual signal. The light source also serves as a nightlight. A preload able pill storage canister is also available, which can be preloaded by a pharmacist and inserted into the dispenser by the patient. This method allows for the dispensing of medical pills with different administration schedules. [4]

The machine is an automatic medicine vending machine that has a self-contained on-site pill dispensing mechanism and a storage facility for multiple pills. It consists of a scanner, servo motors for dispensing medication, large storage space, sensors for pill motion detection, an inventory monitoring system, a vertical foam fill machine for packing medication separately, and a non-contact laser inkjet printer for prescribing time. The inventory monitoring system also keeps track of the expiration date of each batch of medicine and alerts to refill storage when pills

run out. The machine also has an in-built system for receiving user payments for dispensed drugs. The central microprocessor monitors all these systems, actuating and controlling all necessary components to dispense the desired medication. The machine can be viewed as an automated pharmacy on a commercial scale, allowing infinite user access at any time. [5]

The invention relates to an automatic medicine vending machine that has a self-contained on-site pill dispensing mechanism and a storage facility for multiple pills. The machine consists of a scanner, servo motors for dispensing medication, large storage space, sensors for pill motion detection, an inventory monitoring system, a vertical foam fill machine for packing medication separately, and a non-contact laser inkjet printer for printing medicine descriptions. The inventory monitoring system also keeps track of the expiration date of each batch of medicine and alerts to refill storage when the pills run out. The machine also has an in-built system to receive money from the user for the dispensed drugs. All these systems are monitored by a central microprocessor, which is programmed to receive user input via the scanner and control all necessary components to dispense the desired medication. The machine can be viewed as an automated pharmacy on a commercial scale, allowing infinite users to access it anytime. The system can handle a complete range of prescriptions. [6]

Content uniformity (CU) is a critical quality attribute of tablets as a dosage form, ensuring reproducible drug potency. Failure to meet the accepted uniformity in the final product may be caused either by suboptimal mixing and insufficient initial blend homogeneity or may result from further particle segregation during storage, transfer, or the compression process itself. This review presents the most relevant powder segregation mechanisms in tablet manufacturing and summarizes the currently available, up-to-date research on segregation and uniformity loss at the various stages of the production process—the blend transfer from the bulk container to the tablet press, filling and discharge from the feeding hopper, as well as die filling. Formulation and processing factors affecting the occurrence of segregation and tablets' CU are reviewed, and recommendations for minimizing the risk of content uniformity failure in tablets are considered, including the perspective of continuous manufacturing. In routine quality control of solid dosage form manufacturing, CU testing is conducted according to the harmonized rules described in the USP (chapter 905) and Ph. Eur. (chapter 2.9.40). However, the best practice for evaluating the

homogeneity of both blends (as intermediates) and final products, including optimal sampling methods, statistical analysis, and acceptability criteria, is the topic of ongoing discussion. Under this paradigm, mechanisms leading to possible quality failure should be explored and mitigated. Regarding the content uniformity of tablets, it is a common belief that issues with homogeneity especially concern tablets manufactured by means of diagonal compression as opposed to employing wet or dry granulation methods, of which the aim is, among others, to improve tableting blend homogeneity. Industry surveys do not confirm this view, indicating that sufficient drug potency and content are routinely achieved. Nevertheless, unacceptable variability in the API amount or tablet sub- or super potency might be encountered and can stem from different sources. Therefore, two processing causes of failed CU may be broadly identified: suboptimal mixing of ingredients and the failure to meet required blend uniformity as an intermediate, or segregation of initially well-mixed material during handling or compression. This review focuses on the latter phenomenon, i.e., demising and the resulting inhomogeneous distribution of ingredients during various stages of tablet manufacturing, while the topic of blending as a unit operation is outside its scope. Basic mechanisms or types of powder segregation are covered, and testing methods are briefly mentioned. The primary focus of this paper is a comprehensive review of research on blend segregation phenomena related to solid dosage form manufacturing, both as real industrial case studies and simulation studies of which the settings and results can be considered relevant to the pharmaceutical context. The current work aims to fill this gap by focusing on the factors affecting particle segregation and the resulting loss of content uniformity, as well as their mitigation at different stages or operations in tablet production. [7]

The project focuses on designing and developing medicine reminders and dispenser machines for healthcare workers during the pandemic. The goal is to reduce pain, boost physical strength, and maintain health by strengthening the immune system and reducing symptoms. A machine for taking monthly pharmaceutical doses was created to eliminate human contact between patients and caregivers, reducing the risk of virus transmission. Regular meals and exercise routines can help patients adhere to their medication schedules, ensuring correct dosages at the right times. The main objective of the IoT-based smart medical box is to make patient work simple for elderly patients, ensuring they take their prescribed daily medications on time and without skipping any. It also reduces the chance of mistakenly taking too much or too little medication.

The study proposes a smart IoT-based medical box that is simple to use for patients and nurses, monitoring their medications and ensuring correct dosages. The increasing population drives up healthcare costs and overcrowding in care institutions. Mobile technology and biological sensors can help monitor patients' health with remote monitoring systems using sensors to track their heart rate. An alert medicine box was developed for disabled and unable individuals who failed to remember to take their medications on time. A buzzer was added to the box to remind users if they forgot to take tablets or other medicines. [8]

This application aims to identify the shades of colours with exact predictions and their names. A normal human can identify nearly 1 million shades of colour, but those with "enchorial" can only see 1% or 10,000 colours. This is crucial for painting pictures, as a painter needs to identify colour patterns accurately to ensure the reality of the image. Colour detection is a natural process that humans perform naturally, but computers use computer vision to track three different colours: red, green, and blue.

After executing the code, a window redirects to the displayed image, with the path provided as an argument. The colour name of the pixel and the composition of the three colours are obtained. This technology is useful in recognizing colours and in robotics, such as in driverless cars to detect traffic and vehicle backlights, making decisions to stop, start, and continue driving. It also has applications in various image editing and drawing apps. Overall, colour detection is a valuable tool in various fields, including robotics, image editing, and drawing. [9]

This work aims to design a prototype for colour-blind people to help them identify the colours and edges of similar images. Colour-blind individuals are often excluded from professional jobs due to their inability to distinguish between colours. The motivation behind this work is to reduce this deficiency using technology. The proposed setup involves two parts: colour detection and edge detection, which are carried out on a Lab VIEW platform. Images are obtained using a wireless camera in the field of view of a colour-blind person who is unable to identify or judge the colours. Colour-blindness is the inability to differentiate among certain colours, and it affects approximately 8% of men and 1% of women. Edge detection is the detection of significant local changes in intensity in an image, typically occurring on the boundary between two different

regions in the image. Edges have various applications, such as surveillance, text detection, and shape detection.

Researchers have reported various image processing techniques, such as contrast improvement of typhoon cloud images, image segmentation techniques, human ear detection by edge detection and template matching approach, distance measurement, gradient descent method for image segmentation of optic nerves, Signed Pressure Force function for initializing local contour, algorithm for edge detection using threshold technique, recursive detection of edges in colour image based on Green's function approach, colour detection using hierarchical neural networks in RGB space, colour image edge detection using fast vectorial total variation minimization model, colour recognition system by finger interaction method, and traffic light recognition system for colour-blind vehicle drivers.

The aim is to develop an aid for colour-blind people to recognize colour and the edges of images. The proposed setup includes a wireless camera, a TV tuner card for interfacing the camera with a computer, and Lab VIEW IMAQ Vision and Vision Assistant. The acquired image and the processed image with colours will be displayed on the front panel of VI. Lab VIEW provides an opportunity to develop code that could differentiate between colours. [10]

A mobile app for smartphones and tablets was developed to document pressure ulcers, part of the rapidly growing field of mobile health. The app replaces paper-based documentation in healthcare facilities with electronic records. In 2013, a user trial found a high value attributed to wound image galleries in the app and wound tracking through graphing progression. To enhance imaging features, work was undertaken to develop image analysis algorithms for size and colour determination of wounds from wound images taken with an on-board smartphone or tablet camera, using no peripheral hardware or ancillary devices. The work includes three components: mask image, camera calibration, and colour determination. An expert system or machine learning is recommended to enhance the correlation of wound colour to wound stage. The research group previously developed a mobile app called SmartWoundCare for Android and iOS smartphones and tablets to document and assess chronic wounds, specifically pressure ulcers (bedsores).

This paper outlines the application of mobile consumer devices to automated wound analysis and classification. It focuses on developing algorithms to generate wound size and colour from a

wound image taken by a smartphone or tablet camera without the use of peripheral or auxiliary devices such as positioning templates, ultrasonic transducers, or additional lenses. This approach brings novelty to the field of wound management and is in contrast to previous work that controls lighting and wound position with an image capture box [11]

Colour detection is a process that identifies and extracts specific colours from an image or video stream. Python offers a variety of libraries and tools, with OpenCV being a popular choice for computer vision tasks. OpenCV offers various functions and algorithms for colour image processing, making it an ideal choice for colour detection applications. [12]

The paper presents an IoT-based medicine dispenser prototype model designed to assist patients and dependent senior citizens in taking their medications on time, without fail, and without the possibility of missing pills. Inaccurate medications can have severe effects, such as late recovery, severe disease, or even death. The medicine dispenser alarms patients to correctly and accurately take suitable medication and provides instant communication between caretakers and patients.

The Internet of Things (IoT) is an architecture that facilitates the interconnection between people, systems, and devices, addressing issues such as medication non-adherence for patients with chronic infections, which can cause at least 100,000 avoidable deaths and \$100 billion in avoidable medical costs per year. IoT helps create an environment that enables product growth and aids humanity in addressing these challenges. Embedded software in these devices adheres to its functionality and helps deal with ever-growing challenges.

The proposed medicine dispenser uses Arduino Mega, which connects with various system components to create a complete circuit. Pills are contained in respective compartments, and the administrator sets up time in context for each container concerning the medication. At the given time, the alarm buzzer rings, and if the authenticated user unlocks the system, the pills are dispensed. A study conducted by Mahoney, Grey, and Bough at the University of Washington found that 30.6% of volunteers were adherent to medication, and 18.4% of participants were over-devotees with at least one medication. Medication non-adherence to prescribed medicines causes \$100 billion in preventable medical costs in a year and at least 1,000 avoidable deaths.

The paper proposes a prototype of an IoT-based model of a medicine dispenser using fingerprint authentication to address these issues. By ensuring proper medication schedules and reducing the

risk of overconsumption or under consumption, the medicine dispenser can help improve patient outcomes and reduce the risk of adverse drug reactions. [13]

A medication dispensing system consists of an on-site unit and a central monitoring facility. The unit holds bulk amounts of medication in separate receptacles, selects desired dosages based on a prescription regimen, and notifies the patient via an audible or sensory signal. If the patient presses a button within a prescribed time, the dosage is dispensed. If the patient doesn't or the canister isn't dispensed, the unit makes the receptacle inaccessible and contacts a list of caregivers. [14]

III.OBJECTIVES

1. Our project focuses on the issue of regular pill intake, with 21% of patients never following prescriptions and 6% struggling to identify their medications.
2. The tablets are placed on a tray via a dispenser, a voice message is played, and a button is pressed to release them.

IV. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Mismanagement of medication can lead to severe health issues, particularly in elderly individuals, necessitating the development of a system allowing patients to independently take prescribed medications.

1. Physical Separation: This may refer to the systematic arrangement or separation of tablets based on specific criteria such as medication type, dosage, or patient-specific needs.
2. Data Segregation: In technology or data management, it refers to the categorization of tablet devices based on user profiles, applications, or security levels.

V. METHODOLOGY

Fig 1

The system uses a 7805 voltage regulator to convert the 230V power source into a stable 12V DC supply, this regulated power is then distributed to various components, including the conveyer system, camera for image capture, motorized containers, GSM module for communication, Real-Time Clock (RTC) for accurate timekeeping, buzzer for alarm and LED indicators for identification based on colour.

To automate the sorting and dispensing of mixed tablets, install a conveyer system with a unidirectional movement mechanism, for that we make use of a relay system to control the conveyer's operation, ensuring tablets move in a single direction. Later we need to implement a camera system to capture images of tablets on the conveyer and using machine learning code we analyses the images and detect tablet colures. Later we need to create a sorting mechanism that separates tablets based on their detected colures and direct tablets to different containers designated for each colour. Connect the container to a motorized system. We make use of dc motor to control the motor and drop tablets into the designated containers based on colour.

We Integrate a GSM module for communication where we Develop code to send messages to the patient's family members indicating which colored tablet should be taken at a specific time with an alarm using a buzzer. And for the current time we implement a Real-Time Clock (RTC) to track the current time accurately and synchronize the system with the RTC to ensure timely medication reminders. And for indication we connect LEDs to each side of the container, with each LED corresponding to a specific color and activate the LEDs based on the color of the tablet recommended for consumption.

VI. FUTURE SCOPE

The future scope of the IOT Based Smart Tablet Sorter The voice feature aims to enhance the user experience by allowing customizations like calling out the patient's name or saying a personalized phrase. This will make the product more user-friendly. For instance, the Box will sound when it's time to take medicine, like "Good Morning Allen, it's time to take Medicine, two doses of Vitamin D3." The doctor module can be updated to track the patient's medication history and facilitate easy communication with the doctor.

The proposed system aims to provide accurate color representations of colors using CV datasets and 865 colors names, along with RGB and hex values. The system automatically displays RGB color values when the cursor clicks on an image. OpenCV is used for sorting primary colors. The system uses lab VIEW IMAQ vision and a vision assistant for color and edge detection, making it cheap, feasible, flexible, and effective. However, color-blind individuals may struggle to recognize letters written in different colors with different background colors. Future work could involve detecting text by interfacing lab VIEW with the GSM module, which can help color-blind people recognize text.

VII. CONCLUSION

The smart medicine box is a medical device that dispenses medicines according to a prescribed schedule and checks the basic health conditions of patients, such as heart rate, temperature, and oxygen level. It uses biometric recognition to ensure the correct dispensation. The project aims to make the device user-friendly and cost-effective, especially for elderly patients. The device can store three different medicines per patient, which can be enhanced to as many as the user wants. Medication non-adherence is a major problem in the healthcare sector, leading to healthcare resource waste and suboptimal treatment outcomes. This paper reviews technology-based techniques and systems for medication adherence monitoring, highlighting the advantages, disadvantages, and challenges associated with these approaches.

The paper concludes that work is still needed to enhance technology-based systems that can overcome challenges such as accuracy, user comfort, and battery consumption. More clinical trials are needed over long timescales and with large sample sizes to evaluate the accuracy and usability of medication adherence systems. A home-use medication reminder machine and Bluetooth bracelet are proposed, which are simple to use for users who require a machine with

both the pill function and continuous medical tablet/powder bag function. The next design will add sensors to sense picking-up actions and ensure users have taken their medicine.

A system that manages medication adherence, particularly for the elderly, by distributing pills in their respective compartments. The system uses an alarm buzzer to signal when a medication is needed, and if the user unlocks the system, the pills are dispensed. The system also outlines a method to extract the colour field from an RGB image using the openCV platform, which can differentiate monochromatic colours. The paper suggests that future developments in edge detection algorithms could lead to new uses like facial recognition and colour conversion for grayscale images. The technique for identifying the colour and borders of an image is suggested using Lab VIEW IMAQ Vision and Vision Assistant. The work setting is affordable, practical, adaptable, and efficient. The next step is to integrate Lab VIEW with the GSM module to aid in text recognition for colour-blind individuals.

This study presents a prototype for automating the analysis and classification of chronic wounds using mobile devices like tablets and smartphones. The prototype aims to optimize the usefulness of wound photographs generated by the mobile application. Algorithms are created to automatically determine the size of wounds based on prior assessments and real-world size. Additionally, an analysis of the color(s) present in a wound is established. Future research will focus on developing machine learning components and training an expert system to identify the wound stage based on the outputs of other modules that determine size. The goal is to optimize the usefulness of wound photographs and improve the efficiency of chronic wound management documentation. The study also highlights the need for further research to develop machine learning components and train an expert system to identify wound stages based on other factors.

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